

AYURVEDIC DESCRIPTIONS AND PROPERTIES OF MEDICINES USED IN *KATI*,
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ABSTRACT

Basti is a significant Ayurvedic therapy under *Panchakarma*, considered as a specialized treatment that involves external oleation and fomentation. In this technique, warm medicated oil is placed on a dedicated area in a circular frame made of black gram flour. The herbal oil is carefully heated, poured into the dough ring, and retained for a specific amount of time. This treatment is especially effective to reduce muscle stiffness, local tightness, spasm and to increase the strength of bone and joint tissues. *Kati Basti*, *Greeva Basti* and *Janu Basti* are specific Ayurvedic *Panchakarma* therapies that keep warm medicated oil on a particular area using a dough ring, for example, on the lumbar-sacral area, cervical area, knee joint. The main goal of these therapies is to reduce the increase of *Vata Dosh*, pain, stiffness, inflammation, and speed the healing of body. This article elaborates Ayurvedic descriptions and properties of medicines used in *Kati*, *Janu* and *Greeva Basti*.

KEYWORDS: *Ayurveda*, *Kati Basti*, *Greeva Basti*, *Janu Basti*, *Panchakarma*.**INTRODUCTION**

Basti is a well-regarded type of *Panchakarma* therapy that includes the application of comfortably warm, medicated oil, over a specific area of the body e.g. *Kati*, *Pristha*, *Uro*, *Shiro* and *Janu* for a specified time period. *Basti* involves the therapeutic benefits of *Snehana* as well as *Swedana*. The artificial reservoir is created by using dough, preferentially *Masha* and the warmed medicated oil, heated to around 40–45°C, is poured into it. The oil is applied to the patient's skin at a comfortable temperature and maintained when reheated warm oil is added to the artificial reservoir in place of cooled oil, thus maintaining comfort and avoiding burns. *Basti* is helpful for relieving: pain, stiffness, and swelling associated with conditions including arthritis,

spondylosis of the cervical spine, as well as other *Vata-Kapha* variations in disorders of the soft tissues, muscles, or joints. It creates mild sweating, sensory lightness, as well as improves mobility of the treated area while nourishing and strengthening the deeper tissues.^[1-5]

Some challenges or disadvantages are related to the difficulties of positioning the patient, and maintaining an acceptable temperature of the oil to avoid burns. Yet, *Bahya Basti* is a very effective localized treatment for musculoskeletal disorders by reducing pain and inflammation, improving circulation, enhancing flexibility and joint health. There are various types of external *Basti* described in ancient Ayurveda; some of them depicted in **Figure 1**.^[4-6]

Figure 1: Major Types of *Bahya Basti*.

Kati Basti, Greeva Basti and Janu Basti

Kati Basti, *Greeva Basti* and *Janu Basti* are specific Ayurvedic *Panchakarma* therapies that keep warm medicated oil on a particular area using a dough ring. These therapies reduce aggravated *Vata Dosha*, thus relief pain, inflammation and stiffness, etc. These therapies are indicated to treat following conditions:

- ✚ Lumbar spondylosis
- ✚ Sciatica
- ✚ Disc prolapse
- ✚ Ankylosing spondylitis
- ✚ Cervical spondylosis
- ✚ Osteoarthritis knee
- ✚ Rheumatoid arthritis

These therapies are contraindicated for patients with open wounds, active infection, acute trauma, swellings, systemic fever and fractures, etc.^[5-7]

Procedural Protocol

These therapies are delivered in three different sections; *Purva Karma*, *Pradhana Karma* and *Pradhana Karma*. *Purva Karma* is where the practitioner prepare the

patient, cleans the area, and places a dough ring made from black gram flour; *Pradhana Karma* involve pouring of medicated oil that is maintained around 38–45°C into the dough ring, this is performed for a duration of 30–45 minutes while keeping the oil at a consistent temperature; and *Paschat Karma* is where the practitioner removes the oil, cleans the area, and give mild fomentation if needed.

Materials and their properties

Oils that are often used include *Mahanarayana Taila*, *Dhanwantaram Taila*, *Sahacharadi Taila*, *Kottamchukkadi Taila* and *Pinda Taila*, depending on the site and condition. From an Ayurvedic viewpoint, the synergistic effects of *Snehana* and *Swedana* decreases *Vata Dosha*, improves circulation, imparts *Brimhana* and *Srotoshodhana* effects. According to modern point of view these materials exerts their action through vasodilation and relaxation of muscles. Pain modulation, localized anti-inflammatory and analgesic effects of medicines also provides psychosomatic relaxation. The specific mode of actions of *Basti* materials used for *Kati*, *Greeva* and *Janu Basti* is depicted in **Table 1**.^[7-9]

Table 1: Specific mode of actions of Basti materials used for Kati, Greeva and Janu Basti.

<i>Basti</i>	Materials Used	Possible Mechanism of Action
<i>Kati Basti</i>	<i>Mahanarayana Taila</i> and <i>Sahacharadi Taila</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Pacifies <i>Vata</i> in <i>Kati Pradesha</i>, relieves <i>Stambha</i>, reduces pain (<i>Shoola</i>), strengthen <i>Asthi</i> and <i>Mamsa dhatu</i>. ✓ Provides thermotherapy effect improving circulation, muscle relaxation and reducing spasm. ✓ Oils have anti-inflammatory and analgesic phytochemicals.
<i>Greeva Basti</i>	<i>Dhanwantaram Taila</i> and <i>Kottamchukkadi Taila</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Relieves <i>Greeva Shoola</i>, reduces <i>Vata</i> aggravation in cervical region, promote lubrication of cervical joints and soft tissues. ✓ Warm oil reduces cervical muscle tension, improves blood flow, soft tissue mobility, decreases nerve root irritation, and provides mild anti-inflammatory effect.
<i>Janu Basti</i>	<i>Narayana Taila</i> and <i>Pinda Taila</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Pacifies <i>Vata</i> in knee joint, reduces <i>Sandhi Shoola</i>, <i>Shotha</i>, improves flexibility and nourishes joint tissues. ✓ Oil heat reduces stiffness, enhances synovial circulation, decreases local inflammation, improve range of motion. ✓ <i>Pinda Taila</i> specifically reduces burning sensation due to its cooling effect.

These *Basti* therapies are safe, non-invasive and effective in improving mobility, reducing pain, and enhancing quality of life. They can be administered daily or on alternate days, and repeated periodically in chronic cases to maintain long-term benefits.^[8-10]

CONCLUSION

Kati Basti, *Greeva Basti* and *Janu Basti* represent a therapeutic modality of *Panchakarma* in treatment of musculoskeletal disorders that is both effective and localized. By leveraging the actions of *Snehana* and *Swedana*, *Bahya Basti* targets the aggravated *Vata Dosha* which is the predominate component of pain, rigidity and degenerative changes. Medicated oils that are suitable for the condition being treated include *Mahanarayana Taila*, *Sahacharadi Taila*, *Kottamchukkadi Taila*, *Dhanwantaram Taila*, *Narayana Taila*, and *Pinda Taila*; the medicated oil is retained within a dough ring

composed of black gram flour which can both ensure therapeutic penetration and promote localized healing. These therapies offer *Brimhana*, *Srotoshodhana* and *Samvahana* actions in the affected tissues. In more modern contexts the efficacy can be explained through thermotherapy, vasodilation, muscle relaxation, anti-inflammatory property of herbal oils. These approaches are considered beneficial for the management of sciatica, cervical spine spondylosis, osteoarthritis, rheumatoid arthritis and soft tissue injury.

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